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ABSTRACTS

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***In Silico* Study of Clinically Available Antivirals**

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Abstract: Everyone is nowadays aware about the dangerous and tricky nature of viral infections owing to the pandemic. Time and again viral diseases causes endemics or pandemics. In this study we focus on using the FDA approved antiviral drugs to repurpose them for other viral targets and also to find out molecular fragments that may be key to binding to either the structural or enzymatic proteins of the virus, thereby causing an inhibition in its activity. Some key proteins were identified from the literatures. PCA analysis was performed to study the distribution of various compounds in chemical space. We then used the selected FDA approved antiviral molecules, which is a subset of the data available in ViMAL database and performed molecular docking studies. The top molecules were selected for further screening and scaffolds were generated and then a new virtual library was generated. These virtual molecules were docked against the same protein targets as earlier and the results were compared. MD simulation was also performed to calculate the ligand RMSD, Radius of Gyration (rGyr) and other related parameters to support our findings. The study showed that the newly generated virtual molecules showed good binding affinity towards the same pockets.

Keywords: ViMAL, virus, antiviral, molecular docking, molecular dynamics, drug repurposing

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